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High-Pressure Pasteurization and Sterilization System for Liquid Beverages

Abstract

This doctoral study examines the efficiency of pasteurization and sterilization processes for liquid beverages under ultra-high pressure. In traditional pasteurization and UHT (Ultra High Temperature) processes, products are rapidly heated and cooled in jacketed vessels using hot water, steam, and heat exchangers. However, these methods result in significant energy losses and the destruction of beneficial bacteria in the products. This study theoretically explores the feasibility of performing pasteurization and UHT sterilization using a homogenizer under high pressure and presents the first successful application of this technique globally.

Keywords: Ultra-High Pressure, Pasteurization, Sterilization, Homogenizer, Food Safety.

Introduction

Traditional pasteurization and UHT processes are often criticized due to high energy consumption and product quality losses. During these processes, products come into contact with hot surfaces, which can cause burning or a reduction in flavor. Today, the growing consumer demand for more natural, nutrient-rich, and additive-free products has paved the way for the development of new technologies. High-pressure homogenization stands out as a revolutionary technology in the food processing industry. This study explores how pasteurization and sterilization of liquid beverages can be achieved under ultra-high pressure.

High-Pressure Pasteurization and Sterilization System for Liquid Beverages

Pasteurization and UHT (Ultra High Temperature) processes are essential methods used to ensure the safety and extended shelf life of liquid food products. These processes typically involve the rapid heating and cooling of products inside jacketed vessels with the aid of steam, hot water, and heat exchangers.

However, these methods lead to energy losses and negatively affect beneficial microorganisms and nutrients within the product. Particularly during pasteurization, contact with hot surfaces can cause quality degradation, reducing the nutritional value of the products.

This study demonstrates that the use of ultra-high pressure technology can enable pasteurization and sterilization while preserving the product's nutritional value and improving processing efficiency. It has been theoretically proven that pasteurization and UHT sterilization can be achieved using a homogenizer under high pressure, and this method has been successfully implemented for the first time worldwide. Theoretically, for every 50-bar increase in pressure within the homogenizer, the temperature rises by approximately 1°C. Reaching 3,500 bar would result in a 70°C increase, sufficient for effective pasteurization and sterilization. In current systems, heat is applied through the transfer of dry steam or via external jacket surfaces. However, these conventional methods often lead to product adhesion to hot surfaces, causing burning and quality loss.

The heat generated from internal friction occurs when liquids are compressed to extremely high pressures, contributing to the effectiveness of the process. This phenomenon can be expressed as follows:

$$\frac{dT}{dp} = \frac{\beta T}{\rho C_p}$$

Shape 1-a

During the pasteurization process conducted under high pressure, the temperature increase due to internal friction plays a significant role. When liquids are compressed at extreme temperatures, this internal friction causes the product to heat up as it passes through the homogenization valve. The product entering the homogenization valve is squeezed through a narrow space, where friction and physical force push it forward, simultaneously reducing the particle size. Immediately after passing through the valve, the product is rapidly cooled by a cooling exchanger, bringing it to the filling temperature. This process not only ensures the sterilization of the product but also enables the creation of a physically stable, sterile product with a long shelf life. Furthermore, since the product is exposed to the peak temperature at the valve for less than 0.2 seconds, sterilization occurs in this brief period while preserving its properties.

The high-pressure pasteurization system provides physical stability by reducing products to micron levels, allowing them to be stored for extended periods without spoilage at room temperature. Additionally, the system enhances energy efficiency, presenting an environmentally friendly solution. The preservation of the original characteristics and improvement of product quality during the pasteurization and sterilization processes are among the greatest advantages of this technology.

Processing liquid beverages under high pressure makes it possible to maintain nutritional values while achieving energy savings in production processes.

In this project, a system has been designed to achieve homogenization under high pressure while also performing pasteurization and UHT sterilization processes. This work is noteworthy as it is the first of its kind globally and has the potential to revolutionize the food processing sector. High-pressure pasteurization and sterilization not only save energy but also allow for processing without compromising product quality.

In conclusion, ultra-high-pressure pasteurization and sterilization present a groundbreaking innovation for the food industry. This technology offers a more efficient and reliable solution compared to traditional methods, enabling the preservation of product quality and the creation of long shelf-life products. Processing products without altering their natural structure, ensuring microbial safety, and maintaining nutritional values is a significant advancement that meets consumer demands.

Shape1-b

Effects of High-Pressure Applications in Dairy Products

Pressure ranges between 100 and 1200 MPa are considered effective in inactivating foodborne pathogens. This process can be applied to dairy products without compromising their flavor, consistency, texture, and nutritional value, and it can positively influence the processes of curd formation through both microbial and acid coagulation in cheese production. High-pressure applications enable products to reach consumers with a fresh-like presentation by extending shelf life. At the same time, they enhance

the microbial safety of products while preserving their nutritional qualities, allowing for healthy consumption.

This technology provides numerous practical benefits in the dairy industry for producing minimally processed dairy products with high microbial safety standards. Beyond food safety, advantages such as extended shelf life and improved sensory quality make high pressure an important tool in the industry. Consequently, the use of high-pressure technology in the dairy sector is becoming increasingly common to offer consumers healthier and higher-quality products. This method contributes to the development of dairy products with new textures, high nutritional value, and long shelf life.

High Pressure and Cold Processing Techniques in Dairy Products

With the increasing health awareness in modern times, consumers have become more conscious of the components in their food. They now demand natural, nutrient-rich, microbially safe foods with long shelf lives that do not contain chemical preservatives. However, the commonly used high-temperature processes often degrade food quality and lead to nutrient loss. As many heat-sensitive components deteriorate during high-temperature processing, the need for alternative processing methods continues to grow.

High-pressure technology is one of the non-thermal "cold processing" techniques aimed at addressing this issue by processing foods at low temperatures. This technique is employed in of various liquids and solids, such as fruit juices, milk, and canned products, effectively eliminating pathogens while preserving product freshness. In most food applications, the temperature used during processing remains between cooling and ambient temperatures, thereby maintaining the nutritional value and sensory characteristics of the foods.

While energy optimization and heat recovery play significant roles in the development of traditional methods, new preservation technologies offer further opportunities to reduce energy consumption and enhance sustainability in production. Foods processed under high pressure can inactivate pathogenic microorganisms with minimal thermal treatment, extending shelf life and preserving natural freshness. Additionally, applying such processes before drying contributes to increased energy efficiency.

For instance, dairy products exposed to 350 MPa (3,500 bar) pressure significantly reduce foodborne microorganisms. This process can also be successfully applied to liquid food products such as fruit juices, tomato juice, salad dressings, and more, using homogenizers. One of the greatest advantages of high-pressure technology is its ability to produce fresh-like products without the addition of preservatives. At pressure levels above 400 MPa, most plant bacteria are effectively eliminated.

One of the strongest features of this technology is that processing capacity is independent of mass and time. Both liquid and solid foods can be processed under high pressure, effectively eliminating harmful bacteria in raw foods and significantly extending shelf life. Simultaneously, it allows for the production of fresh foods without additives, enhancing the texture of the products. High-pressure processing increases the digestibility of products, providing consumers with healthier options.

The principles of operation for this high-pressure technology are as follows:

Shape 1-c

High-Pressure Application and Use of Homogenizers

Pre-prepared food products are processed through Hommak high-pressure homogenizers, which can reach pressures of up to 3,500 bar after the pasteurization process is completed. During this process, the product is subjected to sudden high pressure and then cooled by reducing the pressure. Once the product reaches the filling temperature, it is filled into sterile containers for storage.

The duration required to create pressure in the container is directly related to the compressibility of the pressure medium and the physical structure of the food. Typically, water is used as the pressure-transmitting medium; however, the presence of air in the food increases the compression time since air is more compressible than water. The isostatic pressure applied is distributed equally throughout every point of the product. After the process is completed, although high pressure is a non-thermal process, there is a slight increase in product temperature due to adiabatic heating. This temperature rise results from internal friction within the fluids and ensures the safe and balanced processing of the product.

Organic Yeast: Helping You Expand Your Organic Food Variety

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the availability of healthy products such as vegan, natural, and organic items in supermarkets. Food producers are compelled to innovate and offer higher-

quality products in this competitive environment. As organic products have become mainstream, consumers are seeking greater variety. These products should be processed as naturally as possible, with limited additives. Organic nutritional yeasts and yeast extracts can provide healthy and nutritious alternatives to various additives, allowing you to diversify your food offerings and meet consumer demands.

Importance of Ultra-High Pressure Systems in Pharmaceuticals

The ultra-high pressure homogenization process, known as micronization in the pharmaceutical industry, is applied to reduce the particle sizes of products. This process occurs under pressures that can reach up to 2100 bar, utilizing turbulence and cavitation effects. Emulsions, suspensions, or solutions are pumped into a high-pressure homogenizer, where particles sized up to 500 microns are reduced to a range of 0.4 to 1 micron. Compared to traditional mixers, colloid mills, or rotor-stator devices, ultra-high pressure homogenization offers better dispersion of active ingredients, resulting in more stable and effective products. This method significantly enhances the quality of pharmaceutical products by reducing particle size and increasing homogeneity.

Ultra-High Pressure Applications in the Chemical and Petrochemical Industries

In the chemical and petrochemical industries, homogenization improves the mechanical properties of products, enhancing their performance. The homogenizers used in this process optimize products in suspension and emulsion forms:

- **Suspension:** Heterogeneous liquid-solid mixtures containing components in both liquid and solid forms.
- **Emulsion:** Heterogeneous structures formed by the combination of multiple immiscible liquids.

Homogenizers increase the stability of these structures, thereby enhancing product quality. This enables the production of more functional and efficient products within the industry.

Impact of Ultra High Pressure

High-pressure homogenization is applied to create more stable emulsions under dynamic conditions. This process increases the surface area of products, reducing the duration and temperature of chemical reactions. Homogenization enhances color intensity in pigments and paints while optimizing the use of additives and allowing for better control of product viscosity. As a result, both the efficiency of chemical processes and the quality of the products are improved.

Ultra High Pressure Applications in Biotechnology

Biotechnology is a field of science aimed at developing plants, animals, and microorganisms using DNA technology, as well as producing new and rare substances that are not found or are insufficient in nature. It has a broad scientific foundation, drawing on disciplines such as molecular biology, microbiology, genetics, physiology, and biochemistry, along with fields like mechanical, computer, and electrical engineering.

Use of Ultra High Pressure Systems in Biotechnology

In biotechnology, high-pressure homogenizers are widely used for cell disruption without the need for solvents or chemicals. This method enables the extraction of high-concentration substances such as enzymes, vitamins, and proteins from cell, bacterial, viral, plant, tissue, and blood samples. High-pressure homogenizers are extremely effective and efficient for these processes, maintaining the highest

quality of the resulting products. This allows for the acquisition of highly pure products in biotechnological applications.

Ultra High Pressure Applications in Cosmetic Products

In the cosmetics industry, high-pressure homogenizers ensure superior quality and control in the production of various products, including skincare items, sunscreens, lipsticks, and perfumes. These devices enhance product homogeneity and improve stability by reducing particle sizes. The reduction in particle size allows for better skin absorption and provides a smoother, more effective texture. Additionally, the homogenization process helps control product viscosity, resulting in high-quality formulations with a long shelf life.

Cosmetic manufacturers worldwide actively use HOMMAK high-pressure homogenizers in the production of emulsions, dispersions, and other formulations. The high precision offered by these homogenizers increases stability and efficiency in production processes. Particularly in next-generation cosmetic products, they facilitate the development of formulations with more natural and effective ingredients by reducing the use of additives. These features have made homogenizers an essential component of cosmetic processing equipment.

Advantages of Ultra High Pressure Use in Cosmetics

The benefits of high-pressure homogenizers in the cosmetics industry include:

- **Reduced Particle Size:** Ensures products have a smoother texture.
- **Homogenization of High Viscosity Materials:** Allows for balanced processing of difficult formulations.
- **Ability to Process Multiple Products with the Same Device:** Enables the production of various cosmetic products using a single system.
- **Uniform Distribution:** Ensures products are homogeneous, enhancing quality.
- **Softer Texture and High Permeability:** Provides products that penetrate the skin better and have a higher effectiveness.
- **Improved Product Quality:** Enhances product performance and customer satisfaction.
- **Adjusts Density and Color:** Achieves formulations that meet desired visual and textural properties.
- **Increased Stability:** Maintains formulation balance and extends shelf life.
- **Extended Shelf Life:** Allows products to be stored for longer without spoilage.

CONCLUSION

High-pressure technology offers innovative solutions that meet the needs of modern consumers prioritizing health, safety, and quality. With a wide range of applications in sectors such as dairy products, food and beverages, chemicals and petrochemicals, pharmaceuticals, biotechnology, and cosmetics, this technology stands out by preserving the nutritional value of products while ensuring long shelf life and high safety standards.

The greatest advantage of this technology is its ability to produce minimally processed, fresh-like products. Particularly in the food sector, it prevents the degradation of heat-sensitive components, enhancing product quality while minimizing the use of additives. Additionally, it contributes to environmental sustainability by promoting energy efficiency. Processes performed under high pressure ensure microbial safety in food by effectively neutralizing pathogens while preserving the sensory and nutritional properties of the products.

In the pharmaceutical industry, this technology enhances the distribution of active ingredients, enabling the production of highly efficient products, thereby improving the bioavailability of micronized solutions and suspensions. In biotechnology, high-pressure homogenization is widely used for critical processes like cell disruption and effective enzyme separation, resulting in improved quality and more effective outcomes for biotechnological products.

In the cosmetics sector, high-pressure technology facilitates the development of better formulations. Reducing the particle size of cosmetic products enhances textural properties and improves skin absorption. It ensures that products remain homogeneous and stable while extending shelf life and increasing customer satisfaction.

In summary, high-pressure technology provides significant advantages not only in terms of quality and safety but also in energy savings and sustainability goals. This innovative technology, applicable across a wide range of industries, enables the production of efficient, safe, and long-lasting products that meet the expectations of modern consumers. In the future, it is expected that this technology will become increasingly widespread, establishing itself as a standard processing method in various fields and adding value to industrial processes.